

EARTH SCIENCES

STRUCTURE OF GABBRO-ANORTHOSITE MASSIFS OF THE UKRAINIAN SHIELD ACCORDING TO GEOPHYSICAL DATA

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Abstract

Three-dimensional gravitational modeling of the Gorodishchensky and Smeleyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs, located in the central part of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton (Ukrainian Shield), has been carried out. A three-dimensional model of the upper crust of the study area was created using maps of the anomalous gravity field at a scale of 1:200,000, considering the results of detailed seismic surveys using reflected wave method and CDP method (common depth point method). Differences in the structure of the intrusive complex were reflected in seismic wave fields, allowing the boundaries of the entire intrusion to be identified. Three-dimensional gravitational modeling was performed to separate rocks of the main composition and rapakivi granites, differing in density, using computer technology for automated interpretation of geophysical data based on the method of optimization. During the iterative process, three different functionals were calculated. It was proved that the joint use of these functionals reduces the amount of noise in the input data. Three-dimensional gravitational modeling allowed for the identification and delineation of the gabbro-anorthosite bodies in the upper part of the cross-section, with a maximum depth of up to 4-5 km. The constructed model, taking into account all available prior information about the density and geometric parameters of anomalous objects, can be used to obtain reliable geological information about the structure of the Gorodishchensky and Smeleyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs.

Keywords: pluton, gabbro-anorthosite massif, upper crust, three-dimensional gravitational modeling, inverse problem, optimization method.

Introduction. Studies of the deep structure of complex multiphase anorthosite-rapakivi and granite plutons are necessary to address many issues: determining the reasons for the appearance of this complex at one of the stages of Earth's crust evolution in the Precambrian on all continents; genesis of rapakivi granites and basic rocks (magmatic crystallization or metasomatic processes); determining the mechanism of pluton formation and the tectonic conditions of their development. This has practical significance, as gabbroids are associated with industrial deposits of tin, beryllium, lithium, tungsten, titanium, vanadium, scandium, phosphorus, and precious and ornamental stones. The Gorodishchensky gabbro-anorthosite massif of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton has been thoroughly studied by geological and geophysical methods. Detailed seismic observations have been carried out in the area of its western contact, which allowed determining the boundaries of the entire intrusion. To separate complexes differing in density, three-dimensional gravitational modeling was performed. This allowed for the identification of gabbro-anorthosite bodies in the upper part of the section, with a maximum thickness of up to 5 km, clarified the shape and size of rapakivi granites, and studied the contacts of the intrusive complex with the enclosing gneisses. In this study, the area of 25x38 km was investigated, and three-dimensional gravitational modeling

of the Gorodishchensky and Smeleyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs was carried out. Seismic surveys in the area of the western contact of the pluton (Gorodishchensky gabbro-anorthosite massif) formed the basis for constructing the first approximation model, as well as in the area of the Smeleyansky massif, located on the eastern contact of the pluton.

Geological and geophysical study of the gabbro-anorthosite massifs of the central part of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton. The Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton, consisting of rapakivi granites and gabbro-anorthosites, covers an area of 7800 km² and is located in the central part of the Ukrainian Shield. It represents a complex multiphase intrusive body that intrudes into the gneisses and migmatites of the Lower Proterozoic metamorphic Ingulo-Inguletsian series. The formation of the pluton occurred in the conditions of a consolidated platform. It is composed of anorthosite-rapakivi and granite formations, including basic, acidic, alkaline, and hybrid types. Rapakivi granites occupy 75% of its area, while gabbro-anorthosites and hybrid rocks of the monzonite series cover 25% of the area. In the pluton area, rapakivi granites form two large massifs, separated by the latitudinal Smeleyansk fault zone: the Korsun-Shevchenkivsky massif in the northern part of the pluton, and the Shpolyansky massif in the southern part (Fig.1).

they stand out as sharp bends in the isolines of Δg . The Smeleyanskaya gravity anomaly covers an area of 400 km² and has a clear north-westward trend. The size of the gravity gradient changes in certain sections of the northeastern and western slopes is 2.5-3.0 mGal/km, while in the area of the north-western slope, it does not exceed -1.5 mGal/km, and on the south-western slope, it is 1 mGal/km. Along the axis of the Smeleyanskaya anomaly, as in the Gorodishchenskaya area, several gravity maxima are observed. The gravity field of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton shows a clear regularity in the distribution of the gravity field, expressed in a zonal distribution of the anomalous field. Areas are distinguished where positive anomalies are located on the periphery of the zonal massifs, and negative anomalies are located in their center. This type of anomaly distribution is observed in the north, south, and partially in the west of the central area of the pluton. In the eastern part of the central area of the pluton, negative anomalies are observed on the periphery of the massifs, while positive anomalies are in the center. The sharply excited gravity field of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton indicates the complex geological structure of this region [1].

Seismic studies. The pluton has been thoroughly studied using various seismic methods. In different years, the following were carried out: deep seismic sounding (DSS); seismic wave exchange method (SWEM); and in the western part of the pluton, in the area of the Gorodishchensky gabbro-anorthosite massif, studies using the reflected wave method (RWM) and common depth point method (CDP) [8]; [5]; [13]; [6]; [14]. The study area is crossed by two DSS profiles in the submeridional profile (XXIV) and latitudinal profile (XXX) directions (Fig. 1). The blast points were located 10-20 km apart. In the case of DSS, they were approximately every 40 km. The length of the geograms reached 220-280 km, and detailed systems of intersecting geograms were set up to ensure structural confidence. The high level of detail in the studies allowed for the acquisition of seismic data that provided nearly unambiguous results, even when using different methods and interpretation techniques [6]; [14]. In the upper part of the Earth's crust of the pluton, at depths of 4-10 km, a layer with reduced velocity was registered, corresponding to the zone of the pluton's intrusive complex.

The main result of using the SWEM was obtaining an objective characteristic of the Earth's crust in the form of a distribution of exchange points, which expresses its heterogeneity and indirectly records the complexity of the geological processes leading to the formation of blocks and structures. According to the earthquake exchange waves in the area of the Korsun-Navomirgorod pluton, in the zone of development of the anorthosite-rapakivi and granite formation, exchangeability (marking the degree of crust heterogeneity) increases, and in the central part, at the latitude of the Gorodishchensky and Smeleyansky gabbro-anorthosite masses, it reaches its maximum values, not only for these profiles but for the entire studied area. To the south of the Smeleyansk sublatitudinal fault, the ex-

changeability of the medium gradually decreases to average levels, and in the zone of its connection with the Novoukrainsky massif, it drops to background values.

The nature of the contact between basic rocks and rapakivi granites inside the pluton is of interest. In the area of the Korosten pluton, such a contact was discovered by the Yurovo-2 well [12]. It represents a complex transitional zone where basic and acidic rocks were subjected to alteration, and thus the physical properties of the contacts change gradually, meaning that the contact is not a sharp seismic boundary. Therefore, separating basic and acidic rocks in the cross-section of the pluton using only seismic data presents significant difficulties. It is logical, in this case, to involve gravitational modeling to solve this problem. In this work, the study area was expanded, and three-dimensional gravitational modeling was performed.

Methodology for interpreting observed anomalies. The method used combines various techniques and approaches to solve the main task — constructing a model of gravitational mass distribution. This process can be divided into several successive stages.

The first stage is the selection of the initial approximation model. At this stage, the qualitative structure of the model is chosen, its quantitative characteristics are determined, and geological information is taken into account.

The second stage is model optimization. To improve the model, an automatic selection of model parameters is performed. Since the objective function is multiextremal, the minimization process is divided into two stages: global search — finding the main minimum, and local search — refining parameters within this minimum. In this case, the selection of an extremum for the local search is done by choosing an initial model and additional constraints.

The third stage is the analysis of solution models and their geological interpretation. The obtained models are assessed, and their correspondence to real geological conditions is evaluated. The evaluation of results involves determining the acceptable limits for parameter values, considering prior data. Thus, this methodology is aimed at determining the internal structure of the Earth's crust based on gravitational data.

Theoretical interpretation algorithm. The computer-based automated system for interpreting geophysical data using the optimization method is frequently used for analyzing gravimetric and magnetometric data. This allows all prior geological information of the study area to be incorporated. Data interpretation consists of two parts:

I. The field $U_{out}(x, y, z)$ or $U_{out}(x, y)$ is given. The function $U_{out}(x, y, z)$ represents the gravity field, its derivatives, or special transformants. For analysis, n most characteristic points are selected, in which the field values are recorded:

$$U_{out}(x_i, y_i, z_i) = U_{out}(i), i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (1.1)$$

II. The interpreter analyzes the observed field, studies all aprior information about the geological structure of the research area, and selects an initial geological model described by parameters:

$$P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\} \text{ or } P^* = \{p_j\}, j = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (1.2)$$

Thus, the initial model is built, and its parameters are set. The next step is to solve the direct problem. In

the selected points, the theoretical field is calculated

$$as: U_t(x_i, y_i, z_i, P) = U_t(i, P), i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (1.3)$$

In equation (1.3), it is indicated that the theoretical field is determined by the model parameters. The functions written in (1.1) and (1.3) are compared, allowing the model parameters to be adjusted to minimize discrepancies between functions (1.1) and (1.3). In solving the interpretation problem, the element $P^* = \{p_j\}$ from (1.2) is chosen for which the discrepancy between the observed and theoretical fields reaches a minimum. To achieve the minimum, a quadratic metric is used, as random errors in the input data are assumed to follow a normal distribution (Gaussian distribution) with zero mean. Therefore, the objective function is minimized:

$$F^{(1)} = F^{(1)}(P) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i [U_n(i) - U_t(i, P)]^2. \quad (1.4)$$

$$\Delta g_n(x_i, y_i, z_i) = \Delta g_n(i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (1.7)$$

is given. It is necessary to find such a function $\Phi(x, y, z)$ - smooth, at least twice differentiable, which can be used to approximate the observed field (1.4 -1.6).

$$P = \{m, (c_x, c_y, h)_j; (2t_x, 2t_y, 2t_z)_j; (\lambda_x, \lambda_y, \lambda_z)_j\}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (1.8)$$

where m is the number of elementary bodies, (c_x, c_y, h) - centers of gravity of bodies,

$$F^2 = \|Un - Ut\|_{L_2}^2 \quad (1.5)$$

a_i where - is the set of weighting coefficients proportional to the absolute values of discrepancies between the observed and theoretical fields. This approach improves the convergence of the iterative computational cycle. If the structure of the functional (1.4) is very complex, a smoothed version is used to simplify the minimization process:

$$F^{(3)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\ln \left| \frac{U_n(i)}{U_t(i, P)} \right| \right] \quad (1.6)$$

Depending on the nature of the input data, different objective functions are used. [4].

The class of rod bodies: three-dimensional model, gravitational field

The approximation model is represented by three-dimensional rods oriented along the coordinate axes, model is defined by the following sequence of parameters:

$(2t_x, 2t_y, 2t_z)$ - length of rods, $(\lambda_x, \lambda_y, \lambda_z)$ - excess linear mass of bodies (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Diagram for describing the three-stripe model.

The centers of symmetry of the rods can change position, allowing for the determination of the location of geometric centers of sufficiently complex structures. This approximation better describes the integral characteristics of the geological model, as evidenced by numerous model calculations [2]; [3]. This model allows obtaining accurate results that are important for

studying the internal structure of bodies and geological interpretation.

Research results and their analysis. The Korsun-Nowomyrgorod pluton is located in a subsided section of the Earth's crust of the Ukrainian Shield, covered by sedimentary rocks up to 100-200 meters thick. The physical properties of the pluton rocks and

their contact characteristics inside the intrusive with surrounding rocks were supplemented with drilling data from the similar Korosten pluton [12]. Rapakivi granites, which dominate the surface of the Korsun-Nowomyrgorod pluton, have a density of 2.59-2.60 g/cm³, and the velocity of elastic waves ranges from 4.87 to 6.35 km/s. Acoustic logging measurements showed that for rapakivi granites, the range of elastic wave velocity is between 5.7 and 6.0 km/s. A feature of these formations is the extremely low degree of velocity differentiation of the rocks, and the acidic rocks of the studied area are almost undetectable for elastic oscillations, which was the basis for distinguishing them in the intrusive complex. The main rocks of the pluton's intrusive complex are diverse in composition and accordingly exhibit a wide range of physical characteristics. Research on samples increasing in basicity, from quartz norite through gabbro-norite to gabbro, clearly shows a variation in density. In the western part of the pluton, in the area of the Gorodyschensky gabbro-anorthosite massif, anorthosites with a density of 2.72 g/cm³, gabbro-anorthosites with a density of 2.79 g/cm³, and gabbro-diabases with a density of 2.93 g/cm³ are widely represented. These rocks appear on the surface along the Olshanka River. Anorthosites and gabbro-norito-

anorthosites are the dominant rocks of the Korsun-Nowomyrgorod pluton, making up to 88% of the area of individual massifs, as confirmed by gravimetric data [9 - 11] They are characterized by the presence of titanium, which increases in the melanocratic varieties of gabbro-norites compared to the Korosten pluton. For the Korsun-Nowomyrgorod pluton, the enclosing rocks of the intrusive complex are gneisso-migmatites of the Ingulo-Inguletskaya series. These are mainly biotite gneisses with a density of 2.65 g/cm³, as well as migmatite layers with a density of 2.6 g/cm³. Modeling was performed using the automated fitting method with gravimetric data from a 1:200 000 scale survey, with a standard deviation in anomaly determination from the Buge survey of about 0.8 mGal.

In the anomalous field (Fig. 3), n=950 characteristic points were collected. Using prior information, an initial approximation model was built, including m=145 elementary objects represented as three-dimensional rod bodies. At the beginning of the iteration cycle, the centers of the sources were located at a depth of h=2 km, with an excess density of -0.05 g/cm³ for rapakivi granites and +0.2 g/cm³ for anorthosites. Initially, the value of the functional was F₀=45166 mGal².

Fig. 3. The central part of the Korsun-Novomirgorod pluton (Gorodyschensky and Smilyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs), isodyne map of the observed gravity field, mGal.

Various methodological approaches were used to solve the problem, including modeling with different initial approximations. The optimal solution to the problem was determined by the average deviation Δ between the observed and theoretical fields. A total of 190 iterations were performed, and a functional value was achieved that allowed describing the anomalous gravitational field with high accuracy. The depth of the disturbing objects reaches 5.07 km, with variations in the upper boundary from 0.01 to 1.0 km, the lower

boundary from 1.4 to 5.07 km, and the depth of the center of gravity of the sources ranges from 0.9 to 2.6 km. The excess density of the bodies ranges from -0.1 g/cm³ to 0.3 g/cm³. Figures 4 (a, b) show the geological structure map of the central part of the Korsun-Nowomyrgorod pluton (Gorodyschensky and Smelyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs) and the depth contour map of the lower boundary with the locations of the geological model bodies.

Fig. 4. The structure of the upper crust of the central part of the Korsun-Novomyrhorodchky pluton (Ukrainian shield) according to the results of three-dimensional gravity modeling: a) geological model of the Gorodyschenskyi and Smilyanskyi gabbro-anorthosite massifs; b) the depth of selected anomaly-disturbing sources.

The difference in values between the observed and model fields in Euclidean metric (L2) is approximately 0.35 mGal, which demonstrates a high level of accuracy in quantitative interpretation. The resulting a posteriori model of the distribution of density inhomogeneities is consistent with the observed data and aprior geological information.

During the research, it was established that the use of various types of functionals for local optimization in fitting methods is quite reasonable. The combined use of quality functionals helps reduce the amount of different types of noise in the observed geopotential fields.

Thus, within the boundaries of the Gorodyschensky and Smelyansky gabbro-anorthosite massifs, the limits of the intrusive complex were defined based on seismic data, and gravitational modeling allowed delineating the main rock massifs in the cross-section.

Conclusions. The Korsun-Nowomyrhorod pluton was thoroughly studied using geological and geophysical methods. Seismic investigations revealed structural features both of the intrusive complex itself and the surrounding Ingulo-Inguletskaya series gneisses, which reflected in the wave fields. This allowed the determination of the boundaries of the entire intrusion, including rapakivi granites and main rock formations. To separate these density-differentiated complexes, three-dimensional gravitational modeling was performed using computer technology for the automated interpretation of geophysical data. For the parameterization of the disturbing sources, an approximation model consisting of three-dimensional rod bodies was used.

The model obtained from the inverse gravity problem revealed the presence of two anomalous bodies: to the west, in the Gorodyschensky massif area, and to the east, in the Smelyansky area. Their maximum thickness reaches 4-5 km, while toward the center of the pluton, the thickness of the main rocks decreases to 2 km, leaving only rapakivi granites on the surface. The greatest thickness of granites and gabbro-anorthosites was recorded at the western and eastern

contacts, where deep-seated disturbances were observed and confirmed by seismic data.

Modeling using the three-rod model showed the high reliability of the computer software, which can be applied to the study of similar massifs. This technology allows investigating the distribution of density both horizontally and vertically, significantly expanding the possibilities of geological interpretation. The obtained models are important for studying the internal structure of gabbro-anorthosite massifs, understanding their origin, and exploring the potential for titanium ore deposits.

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